

Deliverable D7.1 Project Website

28 March 2024

DISCLAIMER

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees, or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein. Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project information

Project title	interSectional INclusion in delibeRation and participatiON with Youth
Acronym	SINCRONY
Project URL	www.projectsincrony.eu
EC Grant Agreement n.	101132459
UKRI grant n.	10099512
SERI grant numbers	23.00494.
Call	HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01-07
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Project start/end date	1 January 2024
Project duration	42 months
EU Project officer	Jarkko Siren
Project coordinator	Elvira Cicognani
Project manager	Valeria Baruzzi

Deliverable information

Deliverable n.	D7.1
Work package n.	WP7
Deliverable title	Project website
Lead beneficiary	WeDo Project intelligence made easy SL (WeDo) - Beneficiary #4
Participants	All partners
Main authors	M.Magaña
Contributors	A.Honrado
Reviewed by	E.Cicognani and SINCRONY UNIBO team members
E-mail Contact for queries	mario@wedo-projects.com
Due date	31.03.2024
Submission date:	28.03.2024
Document status	Final
Document version	V5
Document type*	DEC
Dissemination level	Public / Sensitive

*Legend = R – Report // DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // DEC – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // DMP – Data management plan // OTHER – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

Name of the Entity		Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum- Universita di Bolgna	UNIBO	CO	IT	RTD
2	Universidade do Porto	U. PORTO	BE	PT	RTD
3	Association Europeenne pour la Democratie Locale	ALDA	BE	FR	NGO
4	WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy SL	WeDo	BE	ES	SME
5	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	BE	DK	RTD
6	Turun Yliopisto	UTU	BE	FI	RTD
7	Universitaet Innsbruck	UIBK	BE	AT	RTD
8	Universite de Geneve	UNIGE	AP	CH	RTD
9	The University of Manchester	UNIMAN	AP	UK	RTD

*Legend = Role in the Project: CO – Coordinator // BE – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development// SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // NGO – Non-Governmental Org.

Tab. 1 The SINCRONY Consortium

Work Packages Name		WP Leader
WP1	Coordination and Management	UNIBO
WP2	Co-Design	UNIBO
WP3	Assessment of existing practices in an intersectional lens	UTU
WP4	Power-based analysis of social narratives and experiences	UNIGE
WP5	Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways	ALDA
WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Impact	WeDo

Tab. 2 The SINCRONY Work Packages

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

This deliverable is an open access report, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, if you give appropriate credit to the original author(s). The contributing partners own right on their contents, following the project grant agreement (101132459).

Content

About - Purpose	5
SINCRONY web & Open science	6
The domain, sincronyproject.eu	7
Data collection	7
The target audiences	8
Language, tone & accessibility	9
Desing of the web	12
Structure & Development	13
Key Performance Indicators	14
Website structure	15
Annexes, Website screenshots	17

About Purpose

SINCRONY's project website has been conceived as a centralized platform to communicate and promote the project's efforts towards a meaningful inclusion of youth experiencing social disadvantages and marginalization in deliberative and participatory processes (DPP).

The website will serve as an essential resource for disseminating information about the project, its objectives, activities, and outcomes. It seeks to offer **policymakers, public officials, researchers, educators, youth workers, facilitators of deliberative processes, and youth civil society organizations** concrete tools, guidelines, and solutions to renew the deliberative and participatory practices implemented in public governance and schools.

Through this digital space, the SINCRONY project intends to:

- **Facilitate access to educational and research resources**, including case studies, practical tools, participatory formats, and ethical guidelines designed to improve the democratic quality, inclusiveness, effectiveness, and legitimacy of deliberative and participatory processes.
- **Promote collaboration and knowledge exchange** among the project partners, which includes universities from a wide range of disciplines in social sciences and humanities, a European association of local authorities, civil society organisations, and agencies working on democracy, and a company specializing in communication and dissemination, all together forming a multidisciplinary and multi-methodological pool of expertise and knowledge.
- **Establish a direct communication channel with the project's Stakeholders Collaborative Network**, including expert advisors, municipal representatives, schools, civil society, and youth organizations, to encourage participation and active engagement throughout the whole project life.

SINCRONY web & Open science

The SINCRONY website is founded on the essential principles of Open Science, committing to the promotion of diversity, inclusivity, open access, open data, and scientific education. Through these pillars, we aim not only to advance our project but also to contribute to the development of a more open and collaborative scientific community. In this regard, our approach to open science in SINCRONY lies in the following principles, which are consistently implemented across all project activities, tools and material:

Diversity: We recognize the importance of diversity in science, understanding that the inclusion of different perspectives and experiences enriches research and innovation.

Inclusivity: We strive to remove barriers and create opportunities for everyone, regardless of their situation, to actively participate in scientific processes. This translates into accessible web design, educational content, and the promotion of a science that addresses broader social needs.

Open Access: We strongly believe in open access as a mean to democratize knowledge. All our research results will be made available for free, allowing researchers, educators, and the general public to access our information and resources, thus promoting the dissemination and application of knowledge.

Open Data: The data generated by SINCRONY will be shared under open data principles, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and collaborative use of scientific data.

Scientific Education: The SINCRONY website will have educational resources and foster and promote learning opportunities, directed at both the scientific community and the general public. Our goal is to foster a deeper understanding of how science works for the benefit of society.

The domain **sincronyproject.eu**

It is hosted by: Namecheap, Inc.

Organization name: Namecheap, Inc.

IP address: 162.0.217.22

AS(autonomous system) number and organization: AS22612 Namecheap, Inc.

AS name: NAMECHEAP-NET

Reverse DNS of the IP: server308-1.web-hosting.com

City: Amsterdam

Country: Netherlands

Data **collection**

Data collection through the website will be done mainly through two channels:

- **Project contact email address published at the contact section of the website, allowing visitors to write directly.**
- **Newsletter registration form for visitors to fill in.**

All data collected through the website will be registered and stored in a Smartsheet workspace hosted by Smartsheet Europe under a license owned by WeDo (Beneficiary #4). Data collected will be treated for the sole purpose of the SINCRONY-related communications and will not be shared with any third party.

The target audiences

The target audiences for the SINCRONY project website are divided into two major groups, reflecting different phases and needs throughout the project's lifespan. These phases mark distinct moments in the development and execution of SINCRONY as a project, from its inception to the dissemination of results, including active engagement with young people and with potential users of the project's outputs.

At the beginning of the project, the website is focused on attracting and informing an audience primarily made up of researchers, European Commission's services, including the JRC Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy, multilevel policy makers, and coordinators and partners of other projects working in SINCRONY's related fields. This initial group is essential for establishing a solid foundation of support, collaboration, and theoretical-practical understanding of the project, its goals, and methodologies.

As the project moves towards the dissemination of its findings, the focus of the audience will significantly expand to include educators, youth and youth associations, facilitators of democratic and deliberative processes, and other potential users of the project's outcomes. This stage is crucial to ensure that the findings and tools developed by SINCRONY reach those who can apply them practically in their respective contexts, thus promoting the desired impact on society.

Target Group 1

Researchers and Academics: Specialists in social sciences, politics, education, and other relevant fields interested in deliberative and participatory processes.

European Commission services and policy makers: Officials involved in the formulation of policies related to youth, social inclusion, and education.

Other projects working in SINCRONY-related fields: Leaders of other projects focused on social inclusion, participatory democracy, or civic education.

Universities and Research Centers: Institutions that may be interested in collaborating or learning from the methodologies and approaches of the project, defending and extending democracy.

European Networks of Local Democracies: Organizations that work to strengthen local democracy and promote citizen participation.

Civil Society Organizations: Entities focused on social inclusion, youth rights, civic engagement and civic education.

Target Group 2

Educators and Teachers: Teaching staff in schools and universities who can integrate the project's outcomes into their curriculums and pedagogical practices.

youth and Students: The audience directly benefited by the project, who can use the tools and knowledge for both their personal and community empowerment.

Facilitators of Deliberative Processes: Professionals who lead participatory and deliberative processes in communities, organizations, and in the public sphere.

Youth Workers and Youth Organizations: Entities and professionals who work directly with young people, especially those in disadvantaged situations.

Public Officials and Servants: Especially those in areas of education, social inclusion, and youth, who can apply the project's recommendations and tools in policies and programs.

Civil Society and the General Community: Including non-governmental organizations, community groups, and the general public interested in social inclusion and citizen participation.

Language, tone & accessibility

In the conception and development of the SINCRONY project website, one of the fundamental aspects that has been considered from the start is the adaptability and evolution of the language and tone used, as well as the site's accessibility to ensure that all information is understandable and reachable for all target audiences. In this sense, the website will be initially in English but open to being translated into other languages, especially in the languages where the different pilots will take place.

In the initial phase, the communication tone is predominantly informative, aimed at researchers, academics, policy makers, and other professionals related to the field of social inclusion and citizen participation. This approach has required the use of technical and specific language, with the goal of presenting the project, its objectives, methodologies, and theoretical framework clearly and precisely; at this stage, the website will be in English.

However, aware of the diversity of our audience and with the goal of making the website more inclusive and accessible, **a second update** of the site has been planned. This update will focus on reviewing and adapting the tone and language of certain sections, especially those directed to a broader and more varied audience, such as young people and students, who are direct beneficiaries of the project. A simpler and more direct language will be applied, to facilitate understanding and encourage the interest and active participation of this group, taking into account the local language. The intention is to make the content not only accessible but also attractive to young people, with the objective of promoting greater interaction and engagement with the project's activities and outcomes.

To ensure **universal accessibility of the website**, a plugin has been implemented to facilitate the overall experience of users with functional diversity. This tool is especially useful for people with visual impairments, offering options such as text size adjustment and color contrast, as well as for people with dyslexia, by modifying the typography to facilitate reading.

Engaging Youth through Visual Language and Social Media

Audiovisual language will be a fundamental part of the website, starting from access to the homepage. We will introduce a simple video explaining, through images and key concepts, the importance of giving spaces to young people's voices and why their active participation and contribution to democracy is needed. This type of resources will go hand in hand with social media, which, in the second update, will include TIKTOK and will link directly with content on the website, thus enabling bidirectional traffic.

I feel young!

Design of the web

The website's design will use a colorful, visually appealing, and casual style, being extended to all material that will be developed in the project. The website's visual identity is based on the following principles:

Style: Embrace a unique graphic style that distinguishes the project and accurately reflects its activities, facilitating immediate recognition across a wide range of communication channels, both digital and physical.

Consistency: Ensure brand coherence across all project initiatives, including collaborations and partnerships. We aim to create a sense of unity and cohesion among all generated graphic materials, positioning the website as a central element of our communication strategy.

Architecture: Develop a visual framework aimed at maximizing the project's impact, prioritizing a young audience and offering accessible and appealing language and visual elements.

Communication Strategy and Objectives: Align the visual identity with the website's communication goals. It is essential that the visual elements not only support the project's purposes but also be attractive enough to encourage our target groups to stay and navigate the website.

Structure & Development

The SINCRONY website is designed to facilitate growth and adaptability according to the project's needs, as well as timely communication of results, events, news, and resources.

The website's structure will evolve through two phases, although it is anticipated to be a living entity that adapts according to the project's needs:

Phase 1 (the beginning of the project): The initial upload will include non-confidential general information about the project and data from its partners, links to social media and project pages, as well as legal pages such as data protection, privacy policy, and copyright information, all in line with the principles of Open Science.

Phase 2 (As the project moves towards the dissemination of its findings) : The second upload/update will introduce news, events, and public deliverables pages, promoting transparency and open access to project-related information, in addition to a review in tone and language and message adaptation in order to reach a young audience.

The website will be periodically reviewed and adapted to better meet the engagement needs and objectives, ensuring that the Open Science approach is integrated into the user experience.

Periodic content updates, corrections, and necessary redefinitions for understanding the project will be done every six months. This iterative process will allow all project members to actively contribute to the accuracy, timeliness, and relevance of the content throughout the project's execution.

Website structure

● 1st upload

● 2nd update

Key Performance Indicators

To ensure that the SINCRONY website **keeps people involved, interested, inspired, and informed**, it is crucial to establish clear and measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Using the information provided by Google Analytics, we can track and optimize the website's performance in relation to these objectives. Below are some descriptive texts for each goal:

Keeping People Involved

Our goal is to foster active and sustained participation on the website, offering an attractive user experience that invites visitors to explore and learn about the project.

KPIs:

- **Pages per Session:** The average number of pages viewed during a session. The more pages a user visits, the higher their level of engagement.
- **Average Session Duration:** The average time visitors spend on the site. A longer time indicates greater engagement.

Keeping People Interested

We aim to capture the ongoing interest of our visitors by regularly updating content with relevant information, news, and resources that reflect the latest advancements and activities of the project.

KPIs:

- **Returning Users:** The percentage of visitors who return to the site. A high number indicates continuous interest in the content.
- **Click-Through Rate (CTR) on Featured Content:** Measures the effectiveness of calls to action and featured links in attracting clicks.

Keeping People Inspired

The page aims to be a source of inspiration, highlighting testimonials and case studies that demonstrate the positive impact of the project, encouraging participation and collaboration.

KPIs:

- **Time Spent on Inspirational Pages:** The average time spent on pages that show the positive impact of the project or motivational content.

Keeping People Informed

Our website is committed to providing the most up-to-date and comprehensive information about the project, its objectives, results, and upcoming events, ensuring that all visitors are well informed.

KPIs:

- **Visits to Updates and News Pages:** The number of visits to the project's news and updates sections.
- **Downloads of Resources and Publications:** The number of downloads of documents, reports, and publications, reflecting interest and information acquisition.

By monitoring these KPIs through Google Analytics, we can gain valuable insights into how visitors interact with the website and adjust our strategies to improve involvement, interest, inspiration, and information provided to our audience.

Annexes

Website screenshots

[HOME](#) [ABOUT US](#) [PARTNERS](#) [CONTACT](#)

About the project

SINCRONY is a project dedicated to empowering all youth, especially those belonging to traditionally minority groups. We aim to find new ways to shift power, both between the old and the young, and ensure that it is shared more equally across the younger generation. We will do this by gaining a better understanding of what leads to young people's systematic exclusion from decision making.

Project objectives

Youth engagement

The primary focus of this project is the main protagonist - you. To gain insights into your thoughts, gather your feedback, and address your concerns. How do you envision the future, and most importantly, how can we support you?

Intersectional approach

For everyone. Bringing together all your identities: gender, race, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, disability, and more.

New political practices

The creation of new models is designed to foster the participation and deliberation of all youth, with a particular focus on those at risk of exclusion. These models will be implemented by policymakers, youth workers, and the educational system.

Expected impact

To develop political deliberative and participatory processes, instruments, and solutions for policymakers, public servants, researchers, teachers, and youth workers to revitalize and enhance public governance and educational settings.

Our Approach

An intersectional and multidisciplinary approach encompassing various disciplines within the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities, Psychology, Education, Sociology, Political Science along with the collaboration of European political associations representatives.

Subscribe to our newsletter

Join our mailing list to receive the latest project news

Email Address

[Subscribe](#)

 Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101019147. All participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers. Additional participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers 101019147.

[HOME](#) [ABOUT US](#) [PARTNERS](#) [CONTACT](#)

About the project

Introduction

Throughout Europe, we are witnessing how younger generations are often disregarded as active political decision makers on relevant issues, such as climate change and financial crises that strike globally and affect them above all. This project aims to support youth, especially those belonging to minority groups, in reclaiming the necessary power to inform the European political institutions.

Our pillars

Thoroughly identifying and targeting the factors and processes contributing to the perpetuation of political inequalities and systematic exclusion that limit the participation and deliberation of youth in the political landscape.

Youth engagement

As the protagonists of this project, youth play a central role in it. We will develop activities to obtain valuable insights, and involving local, national, and EU-level stakeholders, including policymakers, public servants, researchers, teachers, youth workers, and European political associations.

Interdisciplinarity

An intersectional team with extensive expertise in the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities, Psychology, Education, Sociology and Political Science, working together towards a common goal.

Open Science

Our commitment is to deliver new processes that are accessible to everyone and can be replicated. To the extent that contextual factors are considered and embedded. The findings will be published and made accessible for capitalization in further research and social actions.

Funding Information

The intersectional iNGusion in deliberation and participation with youth (SINCRONY) is funded by the European Union through the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme.

Facts in brief

- Funding organisations: European Union
- Timeframe: Jan. 2024 - June, 2027
- Funding amount: 2.450.353,75 €
- Coordinator: Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna

Subscribe to our newsletter

Join our mailing list to receive the latest project news

Email Address

[Subscribe](#)

 Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101019147. All participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers. Additional participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers 101019147.

 Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101019147. All participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers. Additional participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by their grant numbers 101019147.

Our partners

WeDo | Project Intelligence Made Easy

WeDo specializes in the management of complex, distributed international research and innovation projects. Based in Barcelona, the company works with the public and private sectors, applying a strategic, holistic team project management approach to creating effective collaborative frameworks for results-driven decision-making. Its multi-disciplinary team of skilled professionals has broad experience in international collaborative projects and EC-funded initiatives since FP6 ICT, Health, Environment, MWT, MHAJ, BSA, BSAHS.

[Visit our website](#)

Miria Marcond Blanch

[LinkedIn](#)

Miria Marcond is Co-founder and CEO. Psychologist and MBA graduate by University Pompeu Fabra. She has broad experience in the planning, coordination, and management of complex research projects, participating in the biomedical sector, and in contact with both the national and the international funding landscape. She has collaborated with foundations, start-up companies, research centers, and universities in leading/coordinating to multi-year, cross-theme, multi-cultural, and multidisciplinary research projects, with broad experience in communication strategies, large meetings, conference organization, and training planning and execution on topics related to EU-funded opportunities, proposal preparation, and project management.

Angel Horrado

[LinkedIn](#)

Since 2004 Angel Horrado has worked as a Project Manager in the planning, management, and implementation of collaborative and multidisciplinary research projects, with total funding of + €30M. He has been directly involved in the preparation and management of more than 50 F&D proposals presented to the EC. He has also worked in the development and implementation of communication and outreach strategies including the organization of workshops and international conferences. Co-founder and Public Funding Manager of Proxim Biotech S.L., a start-up developing a neuroprotective treatment that prevents damage caused by reperfusion after stroke, based on the results of clinical research.

Mario Magaña

[LinkedIn](#)

Mario Magaña, Mario Magaña is an expert in project communications, graphic design, and visual thinking with a Bachelor's in Art (2004), a Master's degree in Corporate Communication (2005), and director of communications at WeDo. He contributes more than 10 years of experience in visual communication and design. He developed communication plans and tools for 14 research projects, including FP6, FP7, and H2020, where he applied his experience in project branding and editors, communication tools and actions, social media management, and outreach material. He contributes to Projects by designing, monitoring, and updating the communication plans in collaboration with partners and stakeholders. He also designs tools for outreach (presenter, social media, videos, leaflets, digital study aids) and supports outreach project actions in general Stakeholder Forum meetings, development of training material and actions, and final project conferences. He coordinates the internal communications of each Project within WeDo, assisting in the development and implementation of tools, templates, procedures, and best practices (e.g. agenda and minutes, Powerpoint, Sharepoint).

Subscribe to our newsletter

Join our mailing list to receive the latest project news

Financed by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101019746. Sincrony is a Horizon Europe Project (101019746) and supported by 10th grant number 101019746.

Grants: Public - Private - Public - Public - Public - Public

HOME ABOUT US PARTNERS CONTACT

Sincrony contacts

<p>Project coordinator Prof. Elvira Cicognani (she/her) Director of the Department of Psychology "Renzo Canestrari" Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna E/ elvira.cicognani@unibo.it</p>	<p>Communication & Dissemination lead Mr. Angel Horrado (he/him) CEO & Project Manager WeDo Project Intelligence made easy E/ comms@wedo-projects.com</p>
---	---

Follow us on

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101019746. Sincrony is a Horizon Europe Project (101019746) and supported by 10th grant number 101019746. Sincrony is a Horizon Europe Project (101019746) and supported by 10th grant number 101019746.

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no 101132459.
UK participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10099512.
Switzerland participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by SERI grant numbers 23.00494.

**Funded by
the European Union**